

High-Performance and Ultrafast Single Germanium Nanowire Photodetectors

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Semiconductor nanowire-based photodetectors with high sensitivity and fast photoresponse in the near-infrared wavelength range are crucial for applications in light-wave communication switches, as well as environmental and atmospheric sensing. However, to advance this field, it is essential to develop innovative fabrication techniques that improve device performance. Here, the fabrication of an axial p–n junction along single germanium nanowires (Ge NWs) and their photoresponse characterization at near-infrared wavelengths are reported. The resulting devices exhibit rectifying current–voltage characteristics with a high rectification ratio in dark conditions and operate with high sensitivity at zero bias under illumination. A high responsivity of 1.72 AW^{-1} , a low noise-equivalent power of $5.68 \times 10^{-11} \text{ W}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$, and a high-frequency response with a 3dB cut-off frequency of 2.85 GHz are determined under 850 nm laser illumination at reverse bias. The high sensitivity of the Ge NW-based photodetectors is ascribed to the radial built-in electric field, which increases the carrier lifetime. In addition, the small size of the Ge NWs results in very small capacitance, leading to very fast response. These results have significant potential for advancing high-speed and low-power photodetectors in next-generation optical communication systems and integrated optoelectronic devices.

physical properties, semiconductor NWs show excellent optical and electrical characteristics such as enhanced light absorption, and higher chemical sensitivity.^[8–11] The NW-based photodetector devices leverage the high surface-to-volume ratio, quantum confinement effects, and the ability to engineer the bandgap in nanowires to achieve high responsivity, fast response times, and sensitivity across a broad spectrum, including the near-infrared (NIR) range.^[12–18]

Most NW-based photodetectors require an external power source to operate, which is needed to separate the photogenerated carriers and generate a photocurrent. However, the dependence on an external power source significantly limits their use in applications such as in-situ medical therapy monitoring and wireless environmental sensing, where self-powered, portable, and low-energy devices are essential.^[19–22] Recently, there has been growing interest in developing photodetectors that can be operated at zero applied bias, making them more suitable for these applications.^[23–25]

These self-powered photodetectors, leveraging the photovoltaic effect, can be classified into Schottky junctions, p–n junctions, and photoelectrochemical cells.^[23–25]

Germanium nanowires (Ge NWs), in particular, offer significant advantages for optoelectronic applications due to their high carrier mobility, compatibility with silicon-based CMOS

1. Introduction

Semiconductor nanowires (NWs) have attracted significant attention as promising candidates for the next generation of nanoscale optoelectronic devices.^[1–7] Because of their unique geometry and

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technology, and lower bandgap compared to silicon.^[26–29] Despite these benefits, there has been limited research on the formation of axial p–n junctions in single Ge NWs, and their photoresponse characteristics remain largely unexplored.^[30–32] This gap in knowledge highlights the need for a comprehensive investigation into the photoresponsivity and overall performance of axial p–n junctions in Ge NWs, which could pave the way for the development of more efficient, self-powered photodetectors for advanced optoelectronic applications.

In this work, single Ge NWs containing an axial p–n junction were fabricated using electron beam lithography (EBL) and inductively coupled plasma reactive ion etching (ICP-RIE). To evaluate the performance of the axial p–n junction-based photodetectors, the key performance metrics such as responsivity, noise-equivalent power, and 3dB cut-off frequency-response were determined.

2. Results

2.1. Dark Current–Voltage Characterization

To evaluate the current–voltage (I – V) characteristics of the axial p–n junctions, a bias was applied to the p-type side of the Ge NWs using a semiconductor parameter analyzer (Agilent, 4156C) while the n-type side was grounded. The applied voltage was swept in the range of ± 1 V under ambient conditions, and the current was measured simultaneously. The typical semi-log I – V curve of a fabricated p–n junction along a Ge NW in dark conditions is shown in **Figure 1a**. The I – V curve indicates rectifying behavior with a high rectification ratio (I_f/I_r) of 110, i.e., the ratio of the forward current (I_f) to reverse current (I_r) at ± 1 V. Since the I – V curves of individual n-type and p-type doped Ge NWs show linear characteristics,^[33,34] the rectifying behavior is related to the formation of a p–n junction along the Ge NW.

To characterize the p–n junction, the single-diode equation was applied to fit the I – V curve in dark conditions. The equation is given as follows:^[35]

$$I = I_s \left[\exp \frac{q(V - IR_s)}{\eta k_B T} - 1 \right] + \frac{V - IR_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (1)$$

where I_s is the saturation current, q is the electron charge, η is the ideality factor, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the temperature, R_s and R_{sh} are the series and shunt resistances, respectively. The fitting curve is shown as a dashed line in **Figure 1a**. The calculated values are summarized in **Table 1**. The obtained ideality factor (3.3) indicates that the generation/recombination mechanism at the trapping surface states is the dominant charge transport process in the p–n junction.^[36]

2.2. Photoresponse Characterization

The photoresponse of the fabricated axial p–n junction-based photodetector was investigated under the illumination of 850 nm laser by varying incident illumination power with and without bias voltage. The actual spot diameter of the laser was about 10 μm .

Figure 1. a) Semi-log current–voltage characteristics of a single Ge NW-based p–n junction in dark conditions and under illumination light @ 55 μW . b) Power law fitting of the obtained photocurrent as a function of laser power, and c) responsivity of the Ge NW based-photodetector as a function of power of illumination with 850 nm laser at zero and applied reverse bias.

Table 1. Rectification ratio (I_f/I_r), saturation current (I_s), ideality factor (η), series (R_s) and shunt (R_{sh}) resistances of the axial p–n junction in dark conditions.

Width [nm]	I_f/I_r	I_s [A]	η	R_s [Ω]	R_{sh} [Ω]
300	110	3.3×10^{-10}	3.3	6.2×10^6	1.9×10^9

Table 2. The estimated maximum values of the photoresponsivity (R_{ph}) and noise-equivalent power (NEP) of the axial p–n junction photodetector under illumination of 850 nm laser without and with applied reverse bias.

Width [nm]	Voltage [V]	R_{ph} [AW^{-1}]	EQE [%]	NEP [W/\sqrt{Hz}]
300	0	0.88	1.28×10^2	1.54×10^{-10}
	1	1.52	2.21×10^2	8.07×10^{-11}
	3	1.72	2.50×10^2	5.68×10^{-11}

The semi-log I – V curves of the fabricated axial p–n junction along a Ge NW in dark conditions and under illumination are shown in Figure 1a. A remarkable photocurrent was observed under reverse and forward bias. Moreover, the current at zero bias was found to be shifted toward the forward bias voltage. This shift is related to the photovoltaic activity, which indicates that the device can be operated without an external power source under illumination.^[37,38] Photocurrent measurements were performed under varied illumination power without and with applied reverse bias voltage. The net photocurrent ($I_{ph} = I_{light} - I_{dark}$) was plotted as a function of laser power with a log–log scale, as shown in Figure 1b. Higher illumination power leads to enhanced electron-hole pair generation, increasing the generated photocurrent. The experimental data were fitted using a power-law relationship, $I_{ph} \propto P^\alpha$, where I_{ph} is the photocurrent and P the input optical power.^[15,35] The exponent α was found to be lower than unity (≈ 0.9), which is related to the existence of localized trap states near the band edges that control the recombination process.^[39]

One measure to evaluate the performance of photodetectors is responsivity (R_{ph}), which is defined as the ratio of the measured photocurrent (I_{ph}) to the incident photon power (P_{in}) in the exposed area of the NW, expressed by:^[40,41]

$$R_{ph} = \frac{I_{ph}}{P_{in}} = \frac{I_{ph}}{\Phi A_{device}} \quad (2)$$

where Φ is the incident optical power density and A_{device} is the effective exposed area of the Ge NW, i.e., the physical surrounding surface area (top and side areas, $37.6 \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2$) of the Ge NW, which is exposed to illumination light. Figure 1c presents the obtained R_{ph} values as a function of laser power for a Ge NW-based photodetector without and with applied reverse bias. The maximum R_{ph} of this particular Ge NW-based photodetector at zero bias was determined to be 0.88 AW^{-1} . As shown in Figure 1c, the photodetectors' responsivity (R_{ph}) decreases as the laser power increases. This decline is because of the saturation of photogenerated carrier concentration at higher excitation power levels. More specifically, increasing the laser power leads to the production of more photogenerated electron-hole pairs. Therefore, a higher proportion of photogenerated electron-hole pairs tends to recombine at the trap states before being collected by the electrodes. Hence, the effective photogenerated carrier concentration and the photocurrent do not increase accordingly, which results in a lower R_{ph} . The R_{ph} was increased under applied reverse bias, as observed in Table 2. At zero bias, the photogenerated electron-hole pairs in the p-type and n-type doped sides of the axial p–n junction-based Ge NW are separated by the axial built-in electric

field at the depletion region of the junction. By applying reverse bias, the depletion region of the p–n junction increases, which leads to a higher electric field and separates a larger number of photogenerated electron-hole pairs. As a result, the photogenerated carriers are easily swept out of the junction, leading to higher R_{ph} .

The external quantum efficiency (EQE) of the Ge NW-based photodetectors was calculated by:^[41]

$$EQE (\%) = \frac{R_{ph}}{\lambda} \times \frac{hc}{e} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where λ is the wavelength (nm), R_{ph} is photodetector responsivity (AW^{-1}) at a particular wavelength (λ), h is the Planck constant, c is the speed of light in vacuum and e is the elementary charge. The obtained values of EQE are summarized in Table 2. This high EQE value above 100% might arise from the enhanced light-matter interaction, which results from the coupling of incident light to leaky mode resonances caused by NWs' geometry, and internal amplification mechanisms like impact ionization.^[42]

Another figure of merit of the photodetectors is sensitivity, which is commonly quantified by the noise-equivalent power (NEP). NEP is defined as the amount of signal power within a 1 Hz bandwidth that results in an output signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of 1, representing the minimum detectable power of the detector. The NEP (in units of W/\sqrt{Hz}) for a given photodetector can be calculated using:^[43]

$$NEP = \frac{P_{in,NI}}{\sqrt{BW}} \quad (4)$$

where $P_{in,NI}$ is the input noise power (W), and BW is the measurement bandwidth (Hz). The $P_{in,NI}$ can be further determined by:^[43]

$$P_{in,NI} = \frac{i_{in,NI}^2}{R_{max}} \quad (5)$$

Here, $i_{in,NI}$ represents the input noise current (A), and R_{max} denotes the maximum responsivity of the detector (A/W). The input noise current $\langle i_n^2(\omega) \rangle$, which is frequency-dependent, can be calculated using methods described elsewhere:^[44]

$$\langle i_n^2(\omega) \rangle = \left[2q \langle i_d \rangle + \frac{4k_B T}{R_{shunt}} + \langle i_{1/f}^2(\omega) \rangle \right] \Delta f \quad (6)$$

The input noise current $\langle i_n^2(\omega) \rangle$ consists of three main components: (i) Shot noise ($2q \langle i_d \rangle \Delta f$) arising from random fluctuations in the device current, which can be determined by measuring the average dark current of the photodetector; thermal Johnson noise ($\frac{4k_B T}{R_{shunt}} \Delta f$) caused by the thermal agitation of charge carriers within the detector, calculated using the operating temperature (T) and shunt resistance (R_{shunt}); and (iii) Flicker noise, which results from the random release of trapped carriers at interfaces, with a power spectral density ($i_{1/f}^2(\omega)$) that decreases as frequency increases, making it challenging to measure during typical device characterization. Accurate estimation of these noise components is critical, as underestimating the noise current leads to an overestimated NEP , which in turn affects the detectivity of the

Figure 2. a) Noise current spectral density of the first frequency component with attenuated laser intensities at zero bias. b) SNR plotted as a function of laser power.

detector by neglecting factors that depend on both intensity and frequency. This omission can result in a misleading evaluation of the photodetector's performance metric.^[45]

To ensure a precise determination of NEP, the noise spectrum of the photodetectors was measured in the frequency domain using a low-noise current preamplifier coupled with a spectrum analyzer. A 850 nm laser, modulated with a 500 kHz square wave and combined with neutral density filters, was employed to adjust the incident light intensity on the Ge NW-based photodetectors from nanowatts (nW) to microwatts (μ W). The NEP of the photodetector was then derived by assessing the photodetector current spectral density in the frequency domain under modulated 850 nm laser illumination across varying laser intensities for a bandwidth of 1 Hz, as shown in Figure 2a. Figure 2b shows the SNR versus input laser power on a double logarithmic scale for the photodetector at zero bias. When the experimental data, which are fitted with a slope of 1, intersect the SNR value of 1, the extrapolated laser power at a 1 Hz bandwidth represents the NEP value. The NEP at zero bias was found to be 1.54×10^{-10} W/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$. Moreover, the NEP of the axial p-n junction-based photodetector was measured under reverse bias (supporting information), summarized in Table 2. The low obtained NEP values under applied reverse bias are comparable with the commercially calibrated Ge detector, measured with the same setup.^[44]

2.3. Frequency-Response Measurement

The photoresponse speed of photodetectors is a crucial factor for their application in light-wave communication switches.^[46] Hence, the frequency-response of the axial p-n junction-based photodetector was investigated with an experimental setup (supporting information), under pulsed photoirradiation of 850 nm laser at reverse applied bias of 3 V, as shown in Figure 3. A standard low-pass filter model was used to fit the experimental data, revealing the 3dB cut-off frequency ($f_{3\text{dB}}$), which indicates the bandwidth of the photodetector.^[47] The bandwidth is the frequency range over which the photodetector can effectively respond to the optical signal. The $f_{3\text{dB}}$ was found to be 2.85 GHz. The collection time (τ) of the photogenerated electron-hole pairs,

defined by $\tau^{-1} = \tau_{\text{tr}}^{-1} + \tau_{\text{r}}^{-1}$, where τ_{tr} and τ_{r} denote the transit time and recombination lifetime, respectively, was estimated to be 193 ps by:^[47]

$$\tau = \frac{0.55}{f_{3\text{dB}}} \quad (7)$$

The obtained response speed of the fabricated axial p-n junction photodetector based on single Ge NW is much higher than the response speed of previously reported group-IV NW-based photodetectors (Table 3).

3. Discussion

Most commercially available photodetectors, made from bulk semiconductors, show responsivity lower than 1 AW^{-1} .^[16] It has been reported that the photodetectors made from semiconductor NWs can exhibit higher responsivity.^[13,15,16,48] The previously reported responsivity (R_{ph}) and collection time (τ) of photogenerated electron-hole pairs for the selected NW-based photodetectors are summarized in Table 3.

Figure 3. Frequency-response of the axial p-n junction photodetector under pulsed photoirradiation of 850 nm laser. A low-pass filter was used to fit the experimental data and to extract the 3dB cut-off frequency.

Table 3. The performance of previously reported NW-based photodetectors. MSM refers to metal-semiconductor-metal configuration with Schottky junction.

Nanowire	Configuration	λ	R_{ph} [AW^{-1}]	τ	Refs.
Ge	MSM	650 nm	1×10^5	–	[16]
Ge-Si	p–n	1.55 μ m	22.60	55 μ s	[19]
Ge	MSM	850 nm	1.75	95 μ s	[49]
Ge	MSM	IR	3.7×10^{-3}	–	[50]
Si	p–n	980 nm	25.11×10^{-3}	310 μ s	[51]
GeSn	MSM	1.55 μ m	70.80	–	[52]
GeSn	MSM	1–3.9 μ m	–	230 μ s	[53]
InGaAs	p–i–n	1.34 μ m	0.67	22 ps	[54]
InAs	BG-FET	500 nm	3×10^4	5 ms	[55]
GaN	p–n	325 nm	3.6×10^2	7 μ s	[40]
InP/InAsP	n ⁺ –i–n ⁺	980 nm	2.5×10^2	55 μ s	[56]
Ge	p–n	850 nm	1.72	193 ps	this work
Ge	p–n	1.55 μ m	27.1×10^{-3}	–	this work

The axial p–n junction-based photodetector in this work demonstrated high responsivity and high photoresponse speed. We can attribute the high responsivity of the fabricated axial p–n junction-based photodetectors to different physical effects. One contribution is related to the collection of photogenerated carriers at the junction due to the axial built-in electric field, and another contribution is associated with the radial built-in electric field caused by the surface depletion layer, increasing the photogenerated carrier lifetime ($\sim\mu$ s).^[57] Also, the small length ($\sim\mu$ m) of photodetectors leads to a negligible loss of photogenerated electron–hole pairs due to the recombination at defect sites. In addition, when the width of NWs is smaller than the light wavelength, optical absorption is enhanced due to strong electromagnetic field confinement and waveguide effects. This sub-wavelength interaction increases the probability of photon absorption by trapping light within the nanowire and concentrating the electric field.^[10,11]

The high-frequency response is related to the effective separation of photogenerated electron–hole pairs and short transit time (\sim ps) of carriers to reach the contacts.^[57] The small size of the Ge NW photodetector results in a few femtofarad (\sim fF) capacitance, which is required for both low-power and high-speed operation.^[54] To further improve the bandwidth of single Ge NW photodetectors, strategies can be focused on reducing capacitance through smaller contacts and optimized geometries; minimizing carrier transit time with high electric fields, shorter nanowires, and surface passivation; and lowering contact resistance via metal selection. In addition, one can improve the material quality by reducing defects and optimizing doping level.

For comparison, the photoresponse of 300-nm-wide axial p–n junction-based photodetector was measured under illumination of an 1550 nm laser diode (supporting information). The responsivity was found to be 27.1 mAW^{-1} at reverse bias (1 V), which is much lower than the one obtained under illumination of 850 nm laser (1.52 AW^{-1}). This can be related to the much lower absorption coefficient of Ge at 1550 nm compared to 850 nm.^[16,41,58] The optical absorption peak of Ge NWs can be shifted from near-

infrared to mid-infrared wavelengths by tuning their band gap via alloying with Sn.^[52,53]

An axial p–n junction photodetector with 50-nm-width was also fabricated and measured under illumination of an 1550 nm laser diode (supporting information). Its responsivity was found to be 11.8 mAW^{-1} at reverse bias (1 V), which is lower than the one obtained for 300-nm-wide axial p–n junction-based photodetector. It was reported that reducing the NW diameter increases the positive and negative photoresponse of the p-type and n-type Ge NWs, respectively, because of the larger impact of the surface trapping states.^[27,49] Moreover, the responsivity is proportional to the carrier mobility.^[59] As we previously reported, the carrier Hall mobility of the individual p-type and n-type doped Ge NWs is reduced by decreasing the NW width.^[33,34] This can lead to a decrease in the photoresponse of the Ge NW-based photodetectors. Therefore, the reason that the fabricated axial p–n junction with 50-nm-wide Ge NW demonstrated lower responsivity compared with its 300-nm-wide counterpart can be related to different factors, including the enhanced negative photocurrent in highly n-type part of Ge NWs, reduced carrier mobility in both p-type and n-type parts, and having a different optical absorption peak.

4. Conclusion

In summary, the axial p–n junction along the single Ge NW was fabricated on the locally P-doped GeOI substrate via EBL and ICP-RIE processes. The fabricated axial p–n junction demonstrated a high rectification ratio in dark conditions. A high responsivity of 1.72 AW^{-1} and an NEP of 5.68×10^{-11} W/\sqrt{Hz} were demonstrated at reverse bias under illumination of 850 nm laser. Moreover, the fabricated axial p–n junction photodetectors demonstrated a high-frequency response with f_{3dB} of 2.85 GHz. We attribute the high responsivity of the fabricated axial p–n junction photodetectors to the axial built-in electric field at the junction, which effectively separates the photogenerated electron–hole pairs, and the radial built-in electric field caused by the surface depletion layer, which increases the photogenerated carrier lifetime. The high response speed is related to the small size of the Ge NW-based photodetector, which leads to very short transit time (\sim ps).

5. Experimental Section

To facilitate the fabrication of axial p–n junction along the Ge NWs for photodetector devices, p-type ($\sim 10^{17}$ cm^{-3}) germanium-on-insulator (GeOI) substrates from SOITEC with a 50-nm-thick top Ge layer and a 200 nm buried SiO₂ layer were used. The fabrication process is described as follows.

Phosphorus Doping of Ge Layer: The GeOI substrates with already exposed rectangular openings (Figure S1, Supporting Information) were implanted locally with phosphorus (P) ions with the energy of 15 keV and the fluence of 5×10^{15} cm^{-2} to convert the p-type doped Ge layer into an n-type doped semiconductor. After ion implantation, rear-side flash lamp annealing (rFLA) with the energy density of 125 Jcm^{-2} was performed for 20 ms to recrystallize the Ge layer amorphized by the ion implantation and in turn to activate the P dopants. The electron concentration of the n-type doped Ge was 1.7×10^{20} cm^{-3} , determined using van-der-Pauw configuration (Supporting Information).

Axial p–n Junction Along the Single Ge NWs: The negative tone resists hydrogen silsesquioxane (HSQ, 2%) was used to expose the NW pattern

Figure 4. a) Top-view SEM image of the axial p–n junction along single Ge NW with an average width of 300 nm with small Ge pads. The vertical black shadow is the resist's residual after ion implantation. b) Optical micrograph of fabricated devices with Ni pads as metal Ohmic contacts.

with EBL. Using the etched markers (Figure S1, Supporting Information), the HSQ pattern of NWs was aligned so that half of the NW is on the P-doped region (n-type) and the other half is on the unimplanted region (p-type) of the Ge layer. To transfer the HSQ pattern of p–n junction NWs into the top Ge layer, ICP-RIE was performed. Afterward, an 80-nm-thick Ni was used for metal Ohmic contacts. A detailed process description regarding Ge NWs fabrication and metal contact formation can be found elsewhere.^[33,34] A top-view SEM image of the axial p–n junction along single Ge NW with an average width of 300 nm and length of 10 μm, and an optical micrograph of the fabricated device after Ni deposition are shown in Figure 4a,b. Despite the challenges in the fabrication process, we successfully fabricated 6–8 working devices, all of which exhibited consistent rectifying behavior.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

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